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DELIVERABLE

D5.3 – Dissemination/Communication Strategy & Kit / Activities Report: 2nd version

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Executive Summary

This document constitutes an update to D5.1– Dissemination/Communication Strategy & Kit / Activities Report Initial version published in Month 6 of the project.

That document established a comprehensive plan for all the Communication, Dissemination, and Liaison activities envisaged by the GREEN-LOG project. It outlined the strategies and approaches to be followed, ensuring effective engagement with identified stakeholders. The plan considered a complete set of activities and channels for effective dissemination and communication of project knowledge and results, including participation in and organisation of workshops and events, scientific publications and policy recommendations, collaboration with relevant initiatives, other projects in the field and the External Advisory Board, etc. Additionally, it outlined the components of the Communication kit, including the brand identity and targeted tools and promotional material such as leaflets, roll-ups, newsletters, videos, project website, and social media accounts. The document also defined the procedures applied to monitor and measure the effectiveness of all communication and dissemination activities. Finally, the major planned capacity building and standardisation activities were briefly presented.

The objective of D5.3 is to build on this, focusing on the Communication, Dissemination, Liaison and Engagement activities carried out in the first 18 months of the project – January 2023 to June 2024. It shifts its attention from the planning for Communication and Dissemination to the main activities and achievements. This includes website and social media updates, publication of news and blog posts, GREEN-LOG Living Lab Workshops, participation in relevant international conferences, cooperation with the sister projects, engagement in the External Advisory Board, further definition of Capacity building, and intermediate Key Performance Indicators, among others. This document will be further updated in two additional moments, with D5.4: Dissemination/Communication Strategy & Kit / Activities Report 3rd Version and D5.5: Dissemination/Communication Strategy & Kit / Activities Report Final Version.

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Table of Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY 2

TABLE OF CONTENTS 4

TABLE OF FIGURES 6

LIST OF TABLES 7

DEFINITIONS, ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS 8

1 INTRODUCTION 9

 1.1 Document Scope 9

2 COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION OBJECTIVES 10

3 TARGET AUDIENCES AND KEY MESSAGES 11

 3.1 Target Audiences 11

 3.2 Mission Statement & Key Messages 12

4 COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES 14

 4.1 Visual Identity 14

 4.1.1 Visuals 14

 4.1.2 Fonts 16

 4.1.3 Deliverable, Minutes, and Agenda templates 16

 4.1.4 PowerPoint Template 17

 4.2 Exhibition Material 18

 4.2.1 Leaflet & Roll-Up 18

 4.3 Press Releases 20

 4.4 Web-based Communication 21

 4.4.1 Website 21

 4.4.2 Blog Posts & News Items 23

 4.4.3 Social Media 24

 4.4.4 Video and Multimedia 26

 4.4.5 Newsletter 27

5 DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES 29

 5.1 Dissemination Events 29

 5.1.1 External Events 29

 5.1.2 GREEN-LOG Events & Workshops 31

 5.2 Scientific Publications 32

 5.3 Policy Recommendations 33

6 TRANSFERABILITY, CAPACITY BUILDING, AND LIAISON ACTIVITIES 34

 6.1 Cooperation with Projects & Initiatives 34

 6.1.1 Cooperation with sister projects 34

6.1.2	Other EU-funded projects	38
6.1.3	Initiatives	41
6.2	Involvement of External Advisory Board	44
6.3	GREEN-LOG Co-creation Living Lab workshops	45
6.4	Capacity Building	49
7	STANDARDISATION ACTIVITIES	52
8	PLANNING AND MONITORING	53
8.1	Roadmap of Activities	53
8.2	Monitoring Tool	55
8.3	Key Performance Indicators	56
9	CONCLUSION	58
	APPENDIX A.....	59

Table of Figures

FIGURE 1: VARIATIONS OF GREEN-LOG LOGO.....	15
FIGURE 2: REFERENCE TO EU FUNDING	15
FIGURE 3: CIVITAS FULL LOGO IN WHITE AND BLUE COLOUR VARIATIONS	15
FIGURE 4: UKRI LOGO	15
FIGURE 5: GREEN-LOG ICONS	15
FIGURE 6: GREEN-LOG ILLUSTRATIONS	16
FIGURE 7: COLOUR PALETTE	16
FIGURE 8: GREEN-LOG DELIVERABLE TEMPLATE	17
FIGURE 9: GREEN-LOG POWERPOINT TEMPLATE.....	17
FIGURE 10: GREEN-LOG LEAFLET (2024)	19
FIGURE 11: GREEN-LOG ROLL-UP	20
FIGURE 12: GREEN-LOG LATEST PRESS RELEASE PROVIDING AN OVERVIEW OF THE PROJECT'S PARTICIPATION AT THE TRA 2024.....	21
FIGURE 13: SCREENSHOT OF THE HOMEPAGE OF GREEN-LOG WEBSITE	22
FIGURE 14: GREEN-LOG WEBSITE: NEWS PAGE	24
FIGURE 15: GREEN-LOG SOCIAL MEDIA PAGES.....	25
FIGURE 16: GREEN-LOG'S 3RD NEWSLETTER	27
FIGURE 17: GREEN-LOG AT URBAN MOBILITY DAYS 2024	30
FIGURE 18: GREEN-LOG AT THE TRA 2024.....	31
FIGURE 19: SISTER PROJECTS COMMON FLYER.....	36
FIGURE 20: SISTER PROJECTS STICKERS	36
FIGURE 21: SISTER PROJECTS JOINT STAND AT THE URBAN MOBILITY DAYS 2023.....	37
FIGURE 22: SISTER PROJECTS JOINT POSTER AT THE TRANSPORT RESEARCH ARENA 2024.....	38
FIGURE 23: GREEN-LOG ISPRA WORKSHOP	46
FIGURE 24: GREEN-LOG BARCELONA WORKSHOP.....	46
FIGURE 25: GREEN-LOG OXFORDSHIRE WORKSHOP	47
FIGURE 26: GREEN-LOG FLANDERS WORKSHOP	48
FIGURE 27: GREEN-LOG ATHENS WORKSHOP	49

List of Tables

TABLE 1: GREEN-LOG TARGET AUDIENCES	11
TABLE 2: GREEN-LOG WEBSITE KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS (M1 TO M18)	22
TABLE 3: GREEN-LOG LINKEDIN KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS (M1 TO M18)	25
TABLE 4: EXAMPLES OF COOPERATION ACTIVITIES WITH OTHER EU-FUNDED PROJECTS	39
TABLE 5: MAJOR COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, LIAISON, AND STANDARDISATION ACTIVITIES	53
TABLE 6: COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES IMPACT	56

Definitions, Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym/Abbreviation	Title
CAV	Connected and Automated Vehicle
DG MOVE	Directorate-General for Mobility & Transport
EAB	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
EIT	European Institute of Innovation and Technology
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
ITS	Intelligent Transport Systems
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LaaS	Logistics-as-a-Service
LL	Living Lab
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Document Scope

The Dissemination/Communication Strategy & Kit / Activities Report: 2nd version (D5.3) is the first update of D5.1, which was the original document serving as the central reference for all Communication, Dissemination, Liaison activities and Engagement strategies for GREEN-LOG.

The objective of D5.3 is to build on this, focusing on the Communication, Dissemination, Liaison and Engagement activities carried out in the first 18 months of the project – January 2023 to June 2024. It shifts its attention from the planning for Communication and Dissemination to the main activities and achievements. It provides updates on planning matters in dimensions in which it makes sense – i.e. Capacity Building. The document reports on the website and social media updates, publication of news and blog posts, GREEN-LOG Living Lab Workshops, participation in relevant international conferences, cooperation with the sister projects, engagement in the External Advisory Board, further definition of Capacity building, and intermediate key performance indicators, among others.

This document will be updated further, with additional versions to be prepared in Months 36 and 42 (D5.4 & D5.5).

2 Communication & Dissemination Objectives

The main objective of GREEN-LOG's Dissemination and Communication activities is to effectively spread knowledge about the project's results to accelerate the take-up of its last-mile delivery solutions.

The specific objectives of the Dissemination and Communication strategy are to:

1. create awareness of the project among the full range of potential adopters/users in the public, and explain how European industry, SMEs, will benefit from the impacts achieved by the project,
2. provide a clear view of the project's concept, goals, and results by formulating adapted key messages, and preparing Communication material,
3. create an active community of potential users and collect feedback to be considered by the project's activities,
4. make the GREEN-LOG brand recognised by the members of European ICT research and cloud constituencies and prepare the ground for the exploitation of the project's results,
5. support targeted dissemination of the project results and accelerate the transferability of the solutions, foster the wide adoption of the project results in Industry and Society.

3 Target Audiences and Key Messages

3.1 Target Audiences

To achieve the Communication, Dissemination, and Liaison objectives of GREEN-LOG, specific targeted messages will be developed based on pre-defined key messages (as described in the next section). These messages will be promoted through a variety of activities to reach various core target groups that make up the naturally interested community around the project.

The main GREEN-LOG target audiences, considering the project's topics and partners involved, are presented in the table below (Table 1).

Table 1: GREEN-LOG Target Audiences

Target Group	Details	Interest in the project
Public Authorities & Policy-Makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local Authorities, City Stakeholders, and other local agencies Road authorities Urban Mobility Planners National Government European Authorities (including the EC) Environmental groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Considering the results in policy and new regulatory developments to green last mile within a coexisting system. Training on project outcomes. Providing new services based on strategic decisions influencing transport optimisation and management processes. Participation in the project's events.
Supply Chain stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Logistic Service Providers/ Freight Forwarders Transport operators Shippers Major retail chains Shop owners & other businesses 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Utilisation of project results. Provision of zero-emission solutions in a cost-effectivemanner. Integration of data-driven services for processes optimisation and reduction of empty loads.
Delivery Solution and Technology developers and providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> OEMs and cargo bike developers EV and delivery bots' solution providers ITS product vendors Engineering tools developers Charging infrastructure providers, Data providers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participation in ecosystem-building events. Exploitation of the project's open-source results. Inspiration for new ideas and applications.
Industry Associations, Technology Clusters and Standardisation Organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> European initiatives and clusters (such as ALICE, ECLF, BDVA, Zero Emissions Urban Fleets (ZEUF)) Associations/ Federations /Network in the relevant area (POLIS, Eurocities, ECTRI) Standardisation organisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inclusion of project's results to collaborative research activities (roadmap, white papers etc.). Dissemination of the project's results to their members. Bilateral participation in events for knowledge exchange.
European projects and initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CIVITAS Initiative and its various stakeholders Expert Group on Urban Mobility Participants, project partners and relevant stakeholders active in the EU-funded projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identification of common topics. Synergies and collaborations for results promotion. Enhancing innovation through results combination. Co-organisation of events.

Researchers and Academia, RTO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individuals engaged in research initiatives and/or working in research/academic institutes • Research communities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Further advance the project's research. • Extension/reuse of the project's innovative technologies. • Inspiration for future research. • Participation in the project's events.
General Public (incl. end users)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Residents, especially of the LLs and the follower cities (i.e., neighbourhood associations, etc.) • End users/customers • Initiatives that leverage public awareness and involvement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Get aware of the benefits offered by the project, • Provide their point of view, • Adopt promotion actions, • Understand the city intervention's impacts.

3.2 Mission Statement & Key Messages

GREEN-LOG is a Horizon Europe funded project which will develop a Logistics-as-a-Service platform for interconnected city logistics, automated delivery concepts using autonomous vehicles and delivery droids, cargo-bike-based innovations for sustainable micro-consolidation and multimodal parcel deliveries integrating public transportation. The approach is deployed and validated in five Urban Living Labs: Athens, Barcelona, Flanders (Ghent, Leuven and Mechelen), Oxfordshire and Ispra. Three follower cities – Arad, Helsingborg, and Valga – will be involved in testing the transferability of the proposed innovations.

To ensure that the messages promoted by GREEN-LOG are always consistent and in line with a wider project-related narrative, below are listed the key messages upon which GREEN-LOG should be promoted:

- Highlight GREEN-LOG's commitment to contribute to low-emission last-mile logistics solutions.
- Showcase cooperative last-mile delivery solutions that are both environmentally friendly and economical, with the use of innovative micro-consolidation arrangements and cleaner delivery methods.
- Highlight the innovation potential of Living Labs for sustainable urban freight, as well as cooperation with all relevant stakeholders, from private logistics operators to local businesses, and citizens.
- Showcase successful case studies: GREEN-LOG should showcase case studies of sustainable logistics practices in different cities to demonstrate their effectiveness and encourage other cities to adopt similar practices.
- Highlight GREEN-LOG's goal of transferability to contribute to sustainable logistics practices all over Europe.
- Encourage the adoption of sustainable logistics practices: GREEN-LOG emphasises the need for sustainable logistics practices, and how they can contribute to reducing greenhouse gas emissions and environmental pollution.
- Highlight the use of innovative technology: GREEN-LOG solutions address technical aspects of innovative concepts such as LaaS, connected services, augmented intelligence modelling platforms, delivery modes such as cargo bikes, electric and autonomous vehicles, etc. to optimise the logistics process and reduce carbon emissions.
- Emphasise the importance of collaboration: GREEN-LOG highlights the need for collaboration between stakeholders, including businesses, local authorities, and

communities, towards a common goal.

- Promote economic benefits: GREEN-LOG should promote the economic benefits of sustainable logistics practices to encourage more companies to adopt them.

The key messages presented are some of the core ideas to be conveyed by GREEN-LOG, which will however be adapted considering the different target audiences it aims to reach.

4 Communication Activities

Communication activities focus on informing, promoting and communicating project activities and results¹. GREEN-LOG envisages a set of communication means and activities currently being used in the project. These are the following:

- GREEN-LOG visual identity,
- Promotional and light-weight exhibition material (leaflets and roll-ups),
- Press releases,
- Web-based communication (website, social media channels, multimedia, videos and newsletters).

These categories of communication are described in the following sections (sections 4.1 - 4.4).

4.1 Visual Identity

4.1.1 Visuals

This section highlights the key visuals, banners, logo, font and colour palette used in all GREEN-LOG dissemination materials and document templates.

A project's communication potential can be greatly improved through effective branding and visual identity. By developing a distinctive and attractive visual identity that is consistently used in all communication materials, target audiences can easily identify and recognise the project. In line with this approach, GREEN-LOG has created its own visual identity to be used consistently across all communication and dissemination materials.

INTRA designers' team developed the logo in the very early stages of the project thus securing a strong brand. We followed an iterative design process and considered the opinions of multiple project partners. The complete process of design of the logo and visual identity is described in detail in D5.1.

The logo acts as an effective and recognisable project trademark and is used in all communication, dissemination and exhibition material supporting the creation of awareness about and promotion of the project. It includes a cargo-bike, as one of the main measures and solutions that will be adopted. Cargo bikes are a type of bicycle that are designed to carry heavy loads or bulky items, in addition to being zero-emission and primarily used in urban environments.

¹ https://rea.ec.europa.eu/document/download/bbeb3f9c-462a-43e1-b362-ae38b766132c_en

Figure 1: Variations of GREEN-LOG Logo

All GREEN-LOG materials include the acknowledgement of EU funding (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Reference to EU Funding

Following the CIVITAS Initiative Corporate Design Guide, the full CIVITAS logo (in any of the available colour variations) is also included in all the communication material. The relevant acknowledgement statement will also be included where relevant.

Figure 3: CIVITAS full logo in white and blue colour variations

Provided that the GREEN-LOG consortium includes partners from the UK whose work in GREEN-LOG is funded by the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI), the UKRI logo is also included in our material.

Figure 4: UKRI Logo

Further, a set of icons and illustrations were created and adapted to GREEN-LOG colours, which can be used in several communication activities (see Figure 5 and 6). Green, blue, and grey have been chosen as the main colours to use for icons and visuals, which are reported below. They have been created paying attention not to generate any gender bias.

Figure 5: GREEN-LOG Icons

Figure 6: GREEN-LOG Illustrations

Figure 7: Colour Palette

4.1.2 Fonts

Comfortaa is a rounded geometric sans-serif type design intended for large sizes. It is available on Google Fonts² and licensed under the Open Font License. It is also available in Greek.

It has been used for headings in the promotional material (e.g. leaflet), website, etc. For body text (on the web) the usage of any modern sans-serif typeface has been suggested. For body text (presentations, deliverables, minutes, agendas, etc.) the default Windows/Mac sans-serif typeface (Arial) has been used.

4.1.3 Deliverable, Minutes, and Agenda templates

The WP5 leader (INTRA) has created the document templates for the project’s deliverables, meeting agenda and minutes, based on the colour palette, the fonts and the logo selected. The

² <https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Comfortaa>

complete information on the designed templates can be found in D5.1.

Figure 8: GREEN-LOG Deliverable Template

4.1.4 PowerPoint Template

The PowerPoint presentation template has been created to be used by the partners for their presentations at all external and internal events, meetings, etc.

Figure 9: GREEN-LOG PowerPoint template

4.2 Exhibition Material

4.2.1 Leaflet & Roll-Up

An initial version of a GREEN-LOG leaflet was produced and uploaded to the project website and distributed to partners for dissemination. The leaflet features an overview of the project's goals, vision, Living Labs and Follower Cities, and solutions to be developed.

The high-quality colour-illustrated GREEN-LOG leaflet comprises a three-fold sheet. A modern and engaging design has been adopted to attract a reader's attention (i.e., a big headline, strong visuals, and a distinct call to action). It has been produced in English by the WP5 leader INTRA, with its layout and content agreed by all the partners.

The printed copies of the leaflet are distributed for dissemination, communication and liaison purposes to target stakeholders during the events, conferences, workshops, and other appropriate fora.

The initially produced leaflet had to be updated considering the change in partnership – namely with ACS SMSA and FedEx Express Greece joining the consortium, and with ELTA no longer being a partner. The figure below shows the up-to-date version of the leaflet. The digital version is available on the project website [here](http://www.greenlog-project.eu).

Figure 10: GREEN-LOG Leaflet (2024)

In the second half of the project after certain milestones are reached, a second, result-oriented, leaflet will be produced, concentrating on a clear vision of the remainder of the project and the lasting impact of GREEN-LOG beyond its run.

Further, a roll-up has been designed to be used during project-organised events, and participation at exhibition stands in relevant conferences (updated with the change in partnership).

Figure 11: GREEN-LOG Roll-up

4.3 Press Releases

Press releases are an important communication tool between GREEN-LOG and appropriate media outlets. Press releases will be written to coincide with important events and organisation of workshops, significant project’s milestones reached, solutions available/tested, major results achieved, outcomes of the Living Labs, etc. This will facilitate a close rapport with specialised media and ensure that project-related news items are disseminated.

Press releases will be disseminated to European and international press, and when relevant, to local and national press. Local partner sites are encouraged to liaise with local media to

inform their end users and citizens about the progress of the Living Labs. Each partner city will translate the general press releases or create their own when appropriate.

A press release template has been created to keep consistency in the layout and structure of the project’s press releases.

The first press release has been issued and shared to be circulated by all partners to their business networks and media contacts, through the databases they maintain, published on the partners’ websites and newsletters, and the external platforms and websites. The press release has also been published on the project website and promoted on social media. It can be found [here](#).

Thus far, GREEN-LOG has published one Press Release, in English³ and Romanian⁴, with a general description of the project, and one in English with an overview of the project’s participation at the TRA 2024⁵ (also translated in Romanian). The Press Releases are available via the website (under the Resources tab).

Figure 12: GREEN-LOG latest Press Release providing an overview of the project’s participation at the TRA 2024

4.4 Web-based Communication

4.4.1 Website

The GREEN-LOG website is accessible under: <https://greenlog-project.eu/>.

The landing page was launched by the end of January 2023, including general info about the project, coordinator contact details, links to social media, and references to EU funding.

This allowed more time for the definition of the website's contents and cooperation with the

³ https://greenlog-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/Horizon-Europe-GREEN-LOG_Press-Release-N1.pdf

⁴ https://greenlog-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/Horizon-Europe-GREEN-LOG_Press-Release-N1_RO.pdf

⁵ https://greenlog-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/GREEN-LOG_Press-Release-N2-1.pdf

selected web developer. POLIS led this task, with the support of INTRA having engaged all partners and most importantly the Living Lab partners, in the content definition (i.e., descriptions of Living Labs, partner descriptions, etc.). The full-content website went online in April 2023.

The GREEN-LOG website serves as the central Communication and interaction gateway by:

- Providing information on the project evolution, including results, publications, news, events, and success stories, including a Blog section, as well as pages dedicated to the Living Labs and Follower Cities,
- Providing access to public deliverables, presentations, photos, digital materials, among others,
- Serving as a dispatching centre for social media channels managed by GREEN-LOG (Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube).

The website has a lean and visually attractive structure, with an easy-to-use Content Management System (WordPress), which facilitates document allocation, and dynamic display of news and events, among others. The tracking of web statistics is compliant with EU data protection regulations, by using Google Analytics. A Privacy and Cookies Policy has been created and made available on the website.

Figure 13: Screenshot of the homepage of GREEN-LOG website

Table 2 shows the main KPIs related to the project website (M1 to M18), namely, visitors, page views, and top pages visited, among others.

Table 2: GREEN-LOG Website Key Performance Indicators (M1 to M18)

Key Performance Indicator	Value
Website Visitors	3400
Page Views	11000
Top Pages Visited	Partners: 753 visits Living Labs: 521 visits News: 492 visits
Main Origins of the Sessions	Search Engines (e.g. Google & Bing): 2200 LinkedIn: 268

Main origins of visitors	United States: 500 users Greece: 389 users Belgium: 301 users Spain: 296 users
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4.4.2 Blog Posts & News Items

Provided that blogging is a critical online method for communicating and engaging with a massive global network of stakeholders, it was agreed to incorporate it into the communication strategy of GREEN-LOG from the start. Blog posts featuring various aspects relevant to the project developments in different Work Packages are directed to relevant target audiences. INTRA coordinates the content collection and publishing, while the partners assigned are responsible for producing the content. Each of the blog posts is accompanied by a relevant eye-catching image.

Blog posts are planned to be published around 1-2 times a month. To structure the blog post publication activities, a plan featuring the partner assigned and the delivery day has been included in the Blog Post Calendar sheet of the online Excel Tracker (see the Tracker description in section 8.2). To support the partners' work, the WP5 leader supplied the consortium with the respective guidelines and useful tips for preparing the blog posts.

A specific strategy for repurposing and reusing the content of each blog post across various channels has been adopted aiming to maximise the impact of each blog post. The WP5 leader will make 1-2 social media (X - formerly known as Twitter- /LinkedIn) posts based on the content/main conclusions of each blog article:

Up to now (M18), 13 blog posts have been published:

- GREEN-LOG – the adventure towards an era of optimised zero-emission last-mile logistics (June 2023)⁶;
- LaaS: How GREEN-LOG Marketplace solution will contribute to a more sustainable last-mile delivery (June 2023)⁷;
- Living Labs for city logistics: The evolutionary journey from birth to maturity (July 2023)⁸;
- Collaboration for optimised last-mile delivery (July 2023)⁹;
- Artificial Intelligence, an opportunity for more sustainable logistics (September 2023)¹⁰;
- Driving Green Logistic with the Help of Synthetic Data (October 2023)¹¹;
- Shaping the Future of City Logistics with New Collaborative Business Models (November 2023)¹²;
- Changing urban freight through the consumer (January 2024)¹³;
- Flanders Paves the Way for Sustainable Logistics through Incentives (February 2024)¹⁴
- Last-mile urban logistics: how AI and simulation are facilitating the shift to sustainability (March 2024)¹⁵;

⁶<https://greenlog-project.eu/green-log-the-adventure-towards-an-era-of-optimised-zero-emission-last-mile-logistics/>

⁷ <https://greenlog-project.eu/market-place-solution/>

⁸ <https://greenlog-project.eu/living-labs-for-city-logistics-the-evolutionary-journey/>

⁹ <https://greenlog-project.eu/cooperation-last-mile-delivery/>

¹⁰ <https://greenlog-project.eu/ai-opportunity-sustainable-logistics/>

¹¹ <https://greenlog-project.eu/green-logistics-synthetic-data/>

¹² <https://greenlog-project.eu/future-city-logistics-collaborative-business-models/>

¹³ <https://greenlog-project.eu/urban-freight-consumer/>

¹⁴ <https://greenlog-project.eu/flanders-sustainable-logistics-incentives/>

¹⁵ <https://greenlog-project.eu/ai-simulation-shift-sustainability/>

- Railways and last-mile deliveries: a partnership for the future (April 2024)¹⁶;
- Green light for greener deliveries: how cities are innovating the last-mile (May 2024)¹⁷;
- From better cars to greener logistics: the self-driving e-cargo opportunity (June 2024)¹⁸.

The website is regularly updated with news items related to the implementation of the Living Labs, presence in conferences/events, and other project results. For instance, a series of news articles focusing on the results of the co-creation workshops carried out in each Living Lab were published. So far, a total of 19 news items have been published on the website.

Figure 14: GREEN-LOG website: news page

4.4.3 Social Media

GREEN-LOG's main social media platform for the project is LinkedIn¹⁹, as it is primarily focused on professional and business-oriented content. Therefore, it is anticipated that stakeholders within the Urban Logistics industry will be attracted to the page. The impact of communication on this channel is tracked through LinkedIn page analytics.

On the other hand, X (formerly known as Twitter)²⁰ is a valuable tool for sharing brief remarks and making announcements that can quickly reach a broad audience or amplify pertinent content through retweets. There are a few matters to consider:

- Tweets are limited to 280 characters,
- Tweets should be accompanied by a relevant image,
- Links are shortened to 23 characters.

¹⁶ <https://greenlog-project.eu/ai-simulation-shift-sustainability/>

¹⁷ <https://greenlog-project.eu/green-light-for-greener-deliveries/>

¹⁸ <https://greenlog-project.eu/from-better-cars-to-greener-logistics-the-self-driving-e-cargo-opportunity/>

¹⁹ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/green-loghe>

²⁰ https://twitter.com/GREENLOG_HE

For both platforms, when posting links, Bitly²¹ has been used to shorten URLs to free up characters. To increase engagement on both networks, several approaches have been taken:

- Hashtags: Hashtags related to GREEN-LOG and Horizon Europe are the following: #GREENLOG_he, #HorizonEU. Other hashtags directly related to the project can be used: #UrbanLogistics #LastMile #LastMileLogistics #LastMileDelivery #ZeroEmissions #Interconnected #UrbanFreight #UrbanLogistics #UrbanLivingLabs #LivingLabs (where appropriate).
- Tagging accounts: Other accounts can be tagged in both images and tweets. Key accounts to tag in tweets are @HorizonEU, @cinea_eu (for Twitter only) and Project Partners Accounts. Particular attention has been paid to tagging the CIVITAS initiative, as well as our sister projects (DECARBOMILE & URBANE),
- Usage of emojis, bold and alternative text is encouraged to make the posts more visually attractive, but also accessible.

A YouTube²² channel has also been created for the GREEN-LOG project. It is used for the promotion of GREEN-LOG videos, together with lectures/materials for the Capacity Building activities.

Figure 15: GREEN-LOG Social Media pages

LinkedIn Page analytics have been used to monitor the impact of communication in this channel. The table below presents an overview.

Table 3: GREEN-LOG LinkedIn Key Performance Indicators (M1 to M18)

Type	Description	Value
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²¹ <https://bitly.com/https://bitly.com/>

²² https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCiO_n4ZnjJyGACyapDEHXWw

Followers	Number of users following the page	620
Unique followers	Number of unique users visiting the page	18670
Page views	Total number of page views	1823
Impressions	Number of times each update is visible for at least 300 milliseconds with at least 50% in view on a (signed in) member's screen	3973
Clicks	Total number of clicks in posts	1645
Shares	Total number of shared posts	59
Median engagement rate	How many times members clicked, liked, commented on, and shared content	9%

As presented in the table, the median engagement rate of GREEN-LOG's page was around 9%. As a reference, statistics have shown that, in 2024, the average engagement rate per post on the platform has been 3.45%²³. This means that GREEN-LOG's engagement rate is above average. The more successful post has reached an engagement rate of 20%.

X (formerly known as Twitter) is the secondary social media page used by the project. In the current reporting period, the page counts 140 followers and has achieved 5471 post impressions.

4.4.4 Video and Multimedia

We envisage a rich set of multimedia content to be produced for presenting the GREEN-LOG project context and solutions, including images and video material.

GREEN-LOG has already produced a project explainer video targeted at the identified target audiences and the general public. This video provides an overview of the project, introduces the 5 Living Labs focusing on their challenges and the major GREEN-LOG innovations, and refers to the Follower Cities and their role. It also highlights the importance of the co-creation and collaboration among various stakeholders in the project. The video has been uploaded to the project's YouTube channel (see the link provided in the section 4.4.3 above), featured on the project's website, widely promoted on social media and shown at the relevant events (i.e. at the TRA 2024 exhibition shared stand).

The project partners (INTRA, FI and UoW) collaborated with the CIVITAS MUSE team to produce the CIVITAS Spotlight video featuring GREEN-LOG. This video hosts selected recordings from the interviews taken from the partners' representatives by the CIVITAS MUSE people during the Urban Mobility Days 2023. The video is available on the project's YouTube channel (see the link provided in section 4.4.3), featured on the project's website as well as on the ALICE ETP GREEN-LOG at the TRA 2024 dedicated page and widely promoted on social media. It's worth mentioning that the video was shared as a GREEN-LOG on CIVITAS Spotlight within the CIVITAS MOVE March 2024 newsletter issue.

The consortium also plans to produce promotional videos in each Living Lab during the demonstration phases. A video tutorial showcasing the integrated GREEN-LOG platform will also be produced, which might also be used for Capacity Building.

The consortium produces images and, whenever it is relevant and possible, also records videos during project events, meetings and other activities (i.e., the Living Lab events), before

²³<https://www.socialinsider.io/blog/linkedin-engagement-rate/#:-:text=However%2C%20the%20main%20takeaway%20of,for%20LinkedIn%2C%20there's%20your%20answer.>

having received permission to do so from all participants. These images and videos will be used for internal and external communication materials (incl. website articles, presentations, reports, etc.). We urge all the partners to contribute multimedia material.

The multimedia material selected from the partners will be collected in a specific folder on the project's internal document repository (SharePoint). Videos are uploaded on the GREEN-LOG YouTube channel (either as public or as unlisted, depending on the content).

4.4.5 Newsletter

Throughout the course of the project, electronic newsletters are regularly created, published, and distributed.

The goal is to keep different stakeholders properly and promptly informed about the project developments. It provides regular updates on what is happening on the project, highlighting its major news and achievements. The newsletters also contain information regarding upcoming tasks and events to inform the audiences on how they can be involved with the project.

The newsletter is shared via Moosend²⁴ to the subscribers, widely promoted via social media, and uploaded to the GREEN-LOG website, under the Resources tab. Thus far, 3 e-newsletters have been sent.

Figure 16: GREEN-LOG's 3rd newsletter

Additionally, GREEN-LOG aims to optimise its Communication and Dissemination capabilities by utilising other exclusive Communication channels within the consortium. Exclusive news

²⁴ <https://moosend.com/>

and/or articles related to the project will be featured in the bi-weekly Polis newsletter (InfoPolis), which has a subscriber base of over 800 individuals from regional and local authorities. For instance, the news item on the conclusions of the GREEN-LOG workshops was promoted via InfoPolis.

Moreover, the project has been liaising with the CIVITAS Initiative's newsletter and other Communication channels, including a feature in the "Project in the Spotlight" (March 2024), and an article on the conclusions of the Living Lab workshops (April 2024).

FGC shares information about the project through their internal newsletter – VIA – sent to their workers. EUT also shares information via their newsletters (one internal, published every week, and monthly bulletins that reach their customers, affiliates, and partners).

5 Dissemination Activities

Dissemination activities focus on making knowledge and results achieved in the project publicly available (free of charge)²⁵. GREEN-LOG anticipates a specific set of targeted activities such as participation and organisation of various dissemination events (conferences, workshops, etc.), publishing in scientific journals and conferences, and publishing of policy recommendations. These dissemination activities are described in detail in the following sub-sections.

5.1 Dissemination Events

5.1.1 External Events

In D5.1, GREEN-LOG identified several high-level national and international events/conferences to promote the project's activities and outcomes, by organising sessions, webinars, workshops, poster sessions, and having a stand in an exhibition area.

We also consider the micro-level events (local & regional events targeted at the local authorities, concerned citizens, local businesses and the general public). In addition, we also envision participation in fairs and industry events (in the second half of the project when more solid results are available). This section reports on GREEN-LOG's event participation during the first 18 months of project implementation. Participation will be either online or in situ, depending on the specific event.

GREEN-LOG partners have been very active in participating in external events to promote the project. During the first 18 months of the project, partners participated in 16 events – with sessions, workshops, pitches and exhibition stands.

Out of these, we would like to highlight the participation of a couple of them.

GREEN-LOG participated in the Urban Mobility Days 2023 in Sevilla, with the Coordinator, WP leaders, and Dissemination and Evaluation managers in attendance. There, the project participated in the **Exhibition Area** with a **stand shared with sister projects**, including a common animated PowerPoint shared on the screen. INTRA presented a short 90 seconds' pitch of the project, in the pitch session. GREEN-LOG also participated in the **CIVITAS Projects Side Events**, which took place one day before the conference (3 October 2023), including Dissemination & Evaluation Managers meetings, where the launch of the **CIVITAS Urban Freight and Logistics Cluster** took place. More information is available on the project's website [here](#).

²⁵ https://rea.ec.europa.eu/document/download/beeb3f9c-462a-43e1-b362-ae38b766132c_en

Figure 17: GREEN-LOG at Urban Mobility Days 2024

GREEN-LOG participated in the Transport Research Arena (TRA) 2024, showcasing its recent accomplishments and inventive solutions to researchers, policy-makers, and industry professionals in the transportation sector. This foremost European transport and mobility research and innovation conference took place from 15 to 18 April 2024 in Dublin, Ireland and gathered more than 4,000 stakeholders. The participating partners showcased GREEN-LOG scope and achievements throughout a broad spectrum of activities, including the following:

- Three poster presentations, including one joint presentation in collaboration with the sister DECARBOMILE and URBANE projects;
- Presence at the EC stand and at the dedicated outdoor exhibition area with the GREEN-LOG solutions being implemented in our Italian Living Lab and demonstrated at the EC Joint Research Centre premises in Ispra (the Yape delivery droid and cargo-bike);
- Project presentation at a Special Session titled “[Innovation in Urban Logistics: Public and Private Sectors Thriving Together](#)” alongside other CIVITAS Initiative projects such as DECARBOMILE, URBANE, DISCO, SENATOR, and LEAD;
- Participation at the TRA 2024 exhibition as a part of the ALICE Innovation Village at the TRA 2024 exhibition, alongside 25 other innovative European projects in urban logistics. Our brand-new video was shown on the dedicated screen, while our experts welcomed interested visitors explaining our work and the latest developments and sharing the project leaflets.

More details are available on the project's website [here](#).

Figure 18: GREEN-LOG at the TRA 2024

5.1.2 GREEN-LOG Events & Workshops

In addition to participation in external events, GREEN-LOG will also organise project-centric events and a final conference.

GREEN-LOG is considering organising its final conference as a part of the [Urban Logistics Innovation Day](#) – an event co-organised by ALICE-ETP and POLIS- first launched in June 2022, as the final conference of the [LEAD](#) Project. Discussions are ongoing, and a final decision will be made closer to the event's date.

In any case, the GREEN-LOG final conference will be organised to present the outcomes and findings of the project and to prepare the ground for further developments and exploitation. In this conference, the academic community will be presented with the results of the project through technical speeches, live demonstrations, and practical application.

Several workshops and webinars are expected to be organised throughout the project, including those for the co-design endeavour in the definition of the Living Lab's activities, and at a later stage to the dissemination of pilot activities and results to external stakeholders. Section 6.3 provides information on already organised GREEN-LOG Living Lab Co-creation workshops.

Moreover, we will explore the possibility of organising workshops and training webinars regarding urban freight transport planning and modelling and innovative delivery methods, sustainable last-mile solutions and the use of GREEN-LOG platform services and tools. Local interactive workshops on the potential transferability and adaptability of the GREEN-LOG solutions developed within the project will also be investigated - further information is given in section 6.3.

The Universities participating in the project will organise workshops throughout the project's duration, where interested researchers and industry professionals can learn about urban freight transport planning and modelling and the requirements of integrated traditional and innovative delivery methods.

In this regard, GREEN-LOG, represented by HALM academic partners, have co-organised a series of Lunch & Learn seminars on “Co-Designing Future Mobility – How to stage cross-sectoral and inter-generational design practices” and “Living Labs: past, now and future”. The two seminars of a series took place on 29/03/2023 and 10/05/2023 respectively at the Halmstad University premises and online. The events were co-organised by GREEN-LOG in cooperation with the EU Horizon Europe project SPINE.

5.2 Scientific Publications

GREEN-LOG will publish articles and scientific papers in specialised media, magazines, and journals, targeting the scientific community, transport professionals, and urban mobility practitioners.

GREEN-LOG considers publishing its innovative research results in the targeted Open Access internationally referred journals, magazines and conferences aiming to increase its academic impact and visibility, but also to connect with the scientific community in the field and disseminate its scientific and technological achievements and results.

All publications should include the following statement:

“This work has been supported by the GREEN-LOG project that has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101069892 and from the United Kingdom Research and Innovation (UKRI) agency. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) or the UKRI. Neither the European Union nor the granting authorities can be held responsible for them.”

The consortium considers (co-)organising 2 special issues in open-access journals. The high scientific profile of the participating academic and research institutes will guarantee the success of these special issues, which will demonstrate the project’s research achievements worldwide.

Coordinating the GREEN-LOG scientific publications in line with the "Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data" in Horizon Europe is a part of the Task 5.2 Data Management Plan and Open Science, led by EUT. More information about the GREEN-LOG publications in Open Access is available in D5.2 Data Management Plan 1st Version. There it can be found the mechanisms to make the scientific publications open.

GREEN-LOG also aims to contribute to Open Research through a range of open peer-reviewed and other types of publications.

The project will explore submitting papers to be published in the European Commission's scientific publishing service, Open Research Europe²⁶. Additionally, GREEN-LOG considers availing of other open-access platforms and tailored services to support the Dissemination of

²⁶ <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>

project results. Many of these platforms are promoted and managed by the European Commission, such as the Horizon Results Booster²⁷ and the Horizon Results Platform²⁸.

To date, GREEN-LOG has one paper published in the scientific journal, namely:

- Exploring Logistics-as-a-Service to integrate the consumer into urban freight, in Research in Transportation Economics²⁹

Three conference papers have been accepted for publication, two have been submitted and one more is planned for submission.

Scientific Publications published by GREEN-LOG partners are made available under the “Resources” tab on the project website. Submission and acceptance of scientific publications **should intensify during the second half of the project, as more outcomes are made available**. The project’s public deliverables will also be made available through the website as soon as they are approved by the Project Officer.

5.3 Policy Recommendations

The lessons learned from the 5 Living Labs and the transferability analysis to the Follower Cities (Valga, Arad and Helsingborg) will serve as a basis for the preparation of policy recommendations to facilitate the Dissemination of sustainable last-mile delivery solutions in European cities.

Given that innovative recent advances in delivery modes (including cargo bikes, connected automated vehicles (CAVs) and distribution strategies (e.g., LaaS) are yet to be implemented or fully integrated into transport networks, there is a need for specific policy support, especially during this era of transition. The disruptive nature of last-mile logistics as well as the collaboration of different stakeholders for network management, demand management, and multimodal deliveries require an orchestrated transition, with careful adaptations, tailored regulations, policy interventions and practical guidelines to ensure resilience and not sacrifice security, safety, data protection, and social inclusion during the transition process. These interventions and guidelines should be included in new sustainable urban logistics plans meeting EU sustainability targets. For example, maximising the integration of micro consolidation centres and cargo bikes into the transport system of a metropolitan area is depending on a series of technical and regulation measures that involve both local and regional/national authorities and careful planning.

GREEN-LOG attempts to support and accelerate this process by presenting policy recommendations on the topics mentioned above. These will follow from pilot testing and quantitative modelling. These recommendations will be summarised in a Roadmap towards zero-emission city logistics based on the GREEN-LOG approach which will be communicated to urban logistics stakeholders across the EU including the EC and ALICE.

As a result of the cooperation with the sister projects (DECARBOMILE and URBANE) to maximise results and outreach capabilities, producing joint policy recommendations has been considered and discussed in the established Working Group 2 focusing on Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation activities. This is one of the many activities planned in the scope of the cluster cooperation – more information can be found in section 6.1.1.

²⁷ <https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/>

²⁸ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/horizon-results-platform>

²⁹ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S073988592300094X>

6 Transferability, Capacity Building, and Liaison Activities

6.1 Cooperation with Projects & Initiatives

Cooperation with other projects and initiatives in the field contributes to the formation of a “large knowledge pool” and therefore often leads to new insights both in research and Dissemination efforts. GREEN-LOG plans liaising with relevant projects and initiatives (in the European Union, but also where relevant, at international level) to exchange information, ideas, and promote innovation. This is also a cost-efficient way to disseminate the project’s concepts and results through the channels and services of the synergy projects/initiatives and promote them beyond the project’s networks.

6.1.1 Cooperation with sister projects

GREEN-LOG capitalises on results, extensive work, and established synergies with several related EU-funded and national research and innovation projects active in the focus areas of GREEN-LOG, including city logistics and last-mile deliveries, starting from the so-called “sister projects” that have been funded by the European Commission under the same call: URBANE³⁰ and DECARBOMILE³¹. Partners use/extend the outcomes of such projects and provide answers to pertinent sustainable last-mile delivery problems.

Joint activities and events that took place until the 30th of June 2023 have been described in the Deliverable D5.1 – Dissemination/Communication Strategy & Kit / Activities Report Initial version. Below we present the updated list of the collaboration actions with the sister projects:

The three projects agreed to create three Working Groups on topics of interest:³²

- *Technical (WG1)*
 - Architecture & tools being developed (Digital Twin, blockchain, etc)
 - Data Management & data spaces
 - Modelling activities
- *Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation activities (WG2)*
 - Joint dissemination & communication opportunities
 - Joint policy recommendations
 - Joint exploitation with industrial aspects
- *LLs & Demos (WG3)*
 - LLs baseline situation & challenges
 - Stakeholders' engagement methodology
 - KPIs definition
 - Common demonstration activities (cf. pilot sites in Spain)

On Organisational aspects the following was decided³³:

- A common SharePoint has been created and is actively used by the projects

³⁰ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/urbane-project/>

³¹ <https://twitter.com/decarbomile>

³² The topics may change following the needs and the developments of the projects

³³ This structure may change adjusting to the organisational needs

- A list of the WGs participants from each project is included in a shared Excel file
- WG calls every 3-4 months (2 hours or as needed)
- Ad-hoc meetings can be organised when needed
- WG leaders:
 - WG1: URBANE
 - WG2: GREEN-LOG
 - WG3: DECARMOBILE
- Cluster Leader rotation approx. every 12 months.
 - Until the end of 2023: URBANE
 - Until the end of 2024: DECARBOMILE
 - Until the end of 2025: GREEN LOG
 - Until the end of Feb 2026: URBANE

Main outcomes and examples of the coordinated activities so far from each WG:

- *Technical (WG1):*
 - The relevant projects' representatives hold regular WG1 calls.
 - The Asset Registry has been created and completed by the projects to map out the assets/ tools being developed by each project to uncover potential collaboration opportunities. This Registry is included in a shared Excel file providing information on the project's main assets' name, description, added value for Living Labs and last-mile network, transferability and interoperability requirements and the responsible partners.
 - A high-level categorisation of the assets based on the city platform concept is being prepared.
 - Further exploiting of the semantic catalogue activities on the cluster level is considered.
- *Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation activities (WG2):*
 - The relevant projects' representatives hold regular WG2 calls.
 - Examples of the coordinated activities:
 - Web-pages dedicated to the sub-cluster on the projects websites (for GREEN-LOG: <https://greenlog-project.eu/cluster/>).
 - Active mutual social media promotion, common LinkedIn page decided to be developed.
 - Common printed material: common flyer presenting the sub-cluster and its goals, puzzle-like stickers with the project logos along with the CIVITAS logo - these were shared at the major events with joint participation.

Figure 19: Sister projects common flyer

Figure 20: Sister projects stickers

- Common motion Power-Point Presentation: slides presenting the sub-cluster, its goals as well as the three project's major facts have been prepared and recorded as MP4 video (shown at the UMD23 exhibition).
- Mutual promotion of the major developments/events in the projects'

newsletters.

- Considering joint activities with regard to Living Labs regulatory frameworks & capacity building, as well as the relevant European workshops.
- Considering applying for the new calls of the Horizon Results Booster when the needs to be covered by the services are clarified.
- Decision on the cluster name and slogan taken during the latest WG2 call (18/06). Name: *Sustainable Last-Mile Logistics Cluster*; Slogan: *Collaborating to Deliver Innovative Solutions in European Cities*
- Events with joint participation (since July 2023)
 - Urban Mobility Days 2023 on 4-6 October 2023 (joint stand).
 - Transport Research Arena 2024 on 15-18 April 2024 (joint paper titled *Decarbonising last mile logistics* presented in a poster session, joint participation in the ALICE Village, participation at the Special Session titled *Innovation in Urban Logistics: Public and Private Sectors Thriving Together*).

Figure 21: Sister projects joint stand at the Urban Mobility Days 2023

Figure 22: Sister projects joint poster at the Transport Research Arena 2024

- **LLs & Demos (WG3):**
 - The relevant projects' representatives hold regular WG3 calls.
 - Each call is dedicated to the topic suggested/most voted by the projects.
 - The projects exchanged information on the Stakeholder's Engagement tools used and lessons learnt. A document providing a global overview of what is existing and how the tools are used in the frame of each project, as well as their benefits and challenges was created.
 - Moreover, the projects shared their definitions of needs and challenges in the frame of their use cases, but also information with regards to the elaboration of the specific methodologies used and implementation processes.

6.1.2 Other EU-funded projects

In addition to the sister projects, GREEN-LOG consortium seeks to create synergies with other European projects.

The initial list of the projects with which GREEN-LOG considers any kind of cooperation has been presented in D5.1. The list is evaluated and updated during the project course based on

the project needs and the input from the whole consortium.

Some examples of the cooperation activities with other EU-funded projects are provided in the table below.

Table 4: Examples of cooperation activities with other EU-funded projects

Project	Brief description	Actions
LEAD	The EU-funded LEAD project designed digital twins of urban logistics to support experimentation and decision-making in public–private urban settings. Finalised in September 2023.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Discussions and activities in the context of the CIVITAS Urban Freight and Logistics Cluster - Social media promotion - Participation in the LEAD Final Event (Urban Logistics Innovation Days 2023) in Brussels on 26/09/2023 with roll-up and leaflets - Participation in a joint Special Session titled “Innovation in Urban Logistics: Public and Private Sectors Thriving Together” which took place on 16/04/2024 as a part of the TRA 2024
ULaADS	Urban Logistics as an On-Demand Service (ULaADS) aims at accelerating the deployment of innovative, shared, zero-emission logistics while addressing the impact of the on-demand economy. Finalised in February 2024.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Discussions and activities in the context of the CIVITAS Urban Freight and Logistics Cluster - Social media promotion - Participation in the ULaADS Final Event in Barcelona on 15-16/11/2023 with roll-up and leaflets.
SENATOR	SENATOR aims to create a new urban logistic model for enhancing the sustainability of cities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Discussions and activities in the context of the CIVITAS Urban Freight and Logistics Cluster - Social media promotion - Participation in a joint Special Session titled “Innovation in Urban Logistics: Public and Private Sectors Thriving Together” which took place on 16/04/2024 as a part of the TRA 2024
UNCHAIN	UNCHAIN aims to create a set of services for optimal and flexible urban logistics operation, management, planning and policymaking, unleashing the potential that technology and digitalisation can bring to sustainable urban logistics and moving towards climate-neutral and smart cities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Discussions and activities in the context of the CIVITAS Urban Freight and Logistics Cluster - Social media promotion - Promotion of the project's activities to GREEN-LOG partners - Sharing a stand at the ALICE Innovation Village at the TRA 2024

DISCO	DISCO aims at fast-tracking upscaling to a new generation of urban logistics and smart planning; enabling the transition to decarbonised and digital cities, delivering innovative frameworks and tools, and changing the Urban Logistics and Planning paradigm with a Physical Internet (PI) – led approach.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Discussions and activities in the context of the CIVITAS Urban Freight and Logistics Cluster - Social media promotion - Participation in a joint Special Session titled “Innovation in Urban Logistics: Public and Private Sectors Thriving Together” which took place on 16/04/2024 as a part of the TRA 2024
MOVE21	MOVE21 aims to transform European cities and their surroundings into smart zero emissions nodes for mobility and logistics.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Discussions and activities in the context of the CIVITAS Urban Freight and Logistics Cluster - Social media promotion - Joint Participation in session at TRA 2024
PIONEERS	PIONEERS addresses the challenges faced by European ports to reduce their environmental impact while remaining competitive and offering added value in a sustainable global trade ecosystem.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Leading the development of different multimodal and flows optimisation experiments. - Scoping and development of a Container Transport Forecast in the Port of Barcelona. - Scoping and development of a Multimodal Inland Planner and Cargo Flow Predictor in the Port of Antwerp-Bruges.
FRONTIER	FRONTIER aims to empower a seamless transition to a revera in transport management leveraging different cutting-edge systems and solutions to create the ultimate integrated network and traffic management systems.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mutual social media promotion - Mutual promotion of the printed material during the events (incl. TRA 2024)
TACTIC	TACTIC, co-funded by the European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT) Urban Mobility, is creating an innovative solution that brings economic, environmental and social value to the last-mile logistics business, involving different stakeholders in the local commerce logistics chain.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cooperation in the submission of a joint abstract to the Open Living Lab Days in Barcelona (September 2023). - TACTIC coordination team participated in the Barcelona Living Lab workshop that took place during the 16th of November.
SPINE	SPINE’s vision is to accelerate the progress towards climate neutrality by reinforcing PT systems through their smart integration with new mobility services, sharing schemes, active transport modes, and micromobility.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-organised Lunch & Learn seminar circled around living lab methodologies on 29/03/2023, - Co-develop a list of ways for engaging in co-creation with users and stakeholders - Co-develop workshop canvases for LL-set-up and orchestration
MARVEL (H2020)	MARVEL aspires the convergence of a set of technologies in the areas of AI, analytics, multimodal perception, software engineering, HPC as part of an Edge-Fog-Cloud Computing Continuum paradigm that goes beyond traditional Big Data, conventional architectures heavily capitalising on distributed resources and heterogeneous data sources in smart city	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mutual activities promotions, sharing with the projects’ consortia - MARVEL was presented by INTRA in the project’s General Assembly #7 in Antwerp.

	environments, while implementing privacy preservation techniques at all data modalities and at all levels of its architecture.	
RE-ALLOCATE (H2020)	RE-ALLOCATE develops integrated and innovative sustainable urban mobility solutions, enabling European cities to exchange knowledge, experiences and ideas, and inspire other cities to replicate and adapt the developed solutions to their own contexts.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mutual analysis of state of the art mobility solutions - Co-develop tailored citizen-engaging co-creation activities for mobility solutions...
ACUMEN (H2020)	ACUMEN proposes a generic, privacy-preserving, data-driven modular digital paradigm for advanced network management, which aims at enabling efficient and reliable door-to-door journeys for people and goods, increased safety and resilience at the network level, and to make a critical contribution to achieving the transport goals set forth in the green deal.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - During 20-24/5/2024 under the ACUMEN project a drones' flight activity in areas of the Athens city centre was organised in order to collect details data on traffic and modal activities on specific areas. This task was executed in collaboration among DAEM, NTUA and Mobilysis. In total 8 areas were mapped and 2 of them are the areas of the 2 parking spaces of DAEM that are engaged for GREEN-LOG. These data will further be provided to GREEN-LOG technical partners to perform potential analysis

6.1.3 Initiatives

GREEN-LOG partners seek to present the project in relevant networks and forums at the European, national or international level focusing on city logistics and enacting decisions on roadmaps and policies based on the project knowledge stemming out of the innovations outcomes, demonstration and transferability actions. The project will aim to participate in the activities organised by these initiatives including meetings, conferences and workshops. The corresponding partners will pursue specific demonstrations and talks, where relevant. Other potential channels for Dissemination of the project's information and achievements include publishing in the newsletters produced by these initiatives, contributing to their publications, publishing on their websites and social media (i.e., re-posting our posts). In addition, GREEN-LOG feeds the collection of best practices presented in other relevant platforms and provides input to relevant European policies and processes.

Having partners with strong involvement in several EU and national initiatives, GREEN-LOG will target these initiatives through its business network.

Collaboration with the CIVITAS Initiative³⁴: CIVITAS is a network of cities, for cities, to achieve cleaner, better connected transport solutions in Europe and beyond through peer-exchange, networking, training, and by encouraging political commitment in support of sustainable mobility. It promotes a collaborative approach for the cities and members of the CIVITAS community to support them in developing innovative solutions, measures, and policies needed for cleaner and better urban mobility. The CIVITAS initiative has established a framework for coordinated evaluation, dissemination and information exchange activities and supports local partnerships in testing and implementing new approaches under real-life conditions.

³⁴ <https://civitas.eu/>

Since GREEN-LOG is linked to the CIVITAS Initiative's main objectives, it is considered a CIVITAS Project which means that it is included in the CIVITAS Liaison and Steward System (LSS) that was developed to support the various projects to interact, contribute and benefit from the CIVITAS Initiative.

GREEN-LOG project, in turn, is playing an active role in the CIVITAS family acknowledging and sharing the CIVITAS objectives and contributing towards them. GREEN-LOG implements the CIVITAS corporate design (in the dissemination material, website, social media), according to the guidelines provided. The consortium will share the project's lessons and conclusions with the CIVITAS network. GREEN-LOG cooperates with the CIVITAS Secretariat and the CIVITAS Communication Team and participates in all relevant CIVITAS-lead meetings and activities. The consortium will share the project's lessons and conclusions with the CIVITAS network.

Examples of the major collaborative actions implemented during the first reporting period:

- Implementing CIVITAS corporate design in all the project material
- Participating to all the relevant CIVITAS Initiative's meetings and activities, including the calls, meetings and activities of the CIVITAS Urban Freight and Logistics Cluster
- Inviting the CIVITAS Communication Team representative to the GREEN-LOG, DECARBOMILE and URBANE mutual Working Group 2 (Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation) call (lead by INTRA / GREEN-LOG). The CIVITAS representative shared with the projects' valuable information and views from the side of CIVITAS Initiative
- Collaborating with CIVITAS MUSE (CSA currently supporting the CIVITAS Initiative) in the producing the CIVITAS Spotlight: The GREEN-LOG Project video. The video is uploaded on the YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FgJcuvKETJQ>
- Contribution to the CIVITAS MOVE newsletter (article "Towards Sustainable Last-Mile Delivery: Insights from GREEN-LOG's Co-creation Workshops" published in the April 2024 issue).
- Active promotion of the CIVITAS events and activities via the project's website, social media and email to the partners.
- Considering participation at the CIVITAS Forum 2024 on 1-3 October in Parma, Italy

Other initiatives of relevance in the areas of sustainable urban mobility include:

ALICE³⁵– A European technology platform set-up to develop a comprehensive strategy for research, innovation, and market deployment of logistics and supply chain management innovation in Europe. GREEN-LOG is about to sign the liaison agreement with the ALICE ETP for mutual support and knowledge exchange. Liaison with ALICE ETP will allow GREEN-LOG to leverage using ALICE network to further disseminate its developments and results to the logistics industry and other relevant stakeholders. On the other hand, the consortium will commit to the activities towards ALICE roadmaps implementation. GREEN-LOG has already been involved in a number of activities and events (co-)organised by ALICE, including the Virtual Breakfast on International Women's Day co-organised by ALICE and POLIS and the IPIC2023, the Urban Mobility Innovation Days 2023 and 2024, the ALICE Innovation Village at

³⁵ www.etp-logistics.eu

the TRA 2024. Moreover, VIL and UoA are members of ALICE and POLIS has established a permanent public-private stakeholder dialogue.

POLIS is a member of the European Commission Expert Group on Urban Mobility, in different working groups, and particularly on the group focusing on Urban Freight and will promote GREEN-LOG activities and results, bringing GREEN-LOG-related topics into policy recommendations and priorities. GREEN-LOG participated with presentation at the POLIS Conference 2023 on 29-30/11/2023 in Leuven, Belgium.

EU Urban Mobility Observatory³⁶ facilitates the exchange of information, knowledge, and experience in the field of sustainable urban mobility in Europe.

BDVA/DAIRO³⁷ is an industry-driven organisation with more than 200 members enabling the data and AI-driven digital transformation in Europe, sustaining Europe's leadership on Big Data Value creation and AI. INTRA leads the Mobility and Logistics Task Force, to which the project seeks to contribute. GREEN-LOG, represented by Amalia Ntemou from Netcompany-Intrasoft, took part at the Data Week 2024 on 12 March 2024, in Darmstadt, Germany. The event was organised by the BDVA under the umbrella of the Data Spaces Symposium 2024.

ZEUF - Zero Emission Urban Fleets is a World Economic Forum initiative focusing on the electrification of urban fleets. Synergies will be explored through POLIS Membership with potential cooperation for common events and others.

European Commission Expert Group on Urban Mobility: To implement the 2021 EU Urban Mobility Framework, a reinforced platform for dialogue and co-creation of actions was announced. This resulted in the reformed Commission Expert Group on Urban Mobility (E03863). In addition, all EU Member States nominated a representative at Ministry level. POLIS is a member of this group, and will bring forth GREEN-LOG related results, whenever relevant.

EARPA³⁸ is the Association of automotive R&D organisations contributing to the European Research Area and the future EU RTD funding programmes. EUT and MOSAIC are members of EARPA. MOSAIC has participated in the EARPA workshops in March 2023 and 2024, as well as participated in the EARPA's FORUM meetings in October 2022 and 2023. Moreover, MOSAIC has positioned itself as Champions in different HE24 proposals and has participated in the elaboration of proposals related to CCAM and logistics together with other EARPAs partners coordinating and as participants.

ERTRAC³⁹, the European Road Transport Research Advisory Council, is the European Technology Platform (ETP) for Road Transport. ERTRAC is recognised and supported by the European Commission. POLIS is a member of ERTRAC and co-leader of its Urban Mobility Working Group. POLIS will bring in relevant topics from GREEN-LOG that require future research needs to put them on the agenda.

ECTRI⁴⁰ is a European research association for sustainable and multimodal mobility providing competence, knowledge and advice towards green, safe, efficient, and inclusive transport. UoA and UAEGEAN have strong connections with members of ECTRI. GREEN-LOG was presented

³⁶ https://urban-mobility-observatory.transport.ec.europa.eu/index_en

³⁷ <https://www.bdva.eu/>

³⁸ <https://www.earpa.eu>

³⁹ <https://www.ertrac.org/>

⁴⁰ <https://www.ectri.org>

at the Special Session titled “Innovation in Urban Logistics: Public and Private Sectors Thriving Together” at the TRA 2024, co-organised in cooperation with ALICE and ECTRI representatives.

ECLF⁴¹ aims to develop and help implement a strategy, for transferring as much as possible of the freight/goods being moved within the urban environment in Europe, from motorised vehicles to cycles. In addition, ECLF will support any business or social enterprise which uses or intends to use cargo bikes and other cycles to deliver its operations or services. VIL is active in ECLF. First contact was made with ECLF and the goals of GREEN-LOG were explained. Further collaboration will be continued after the first demonstration phase for gathering their insights.

EUROCITIES⁴²: Athens, Ghent and Leuven are members of the EUROCITIES community of cities.

6.2 Involvement of External Advisory Board

To ensure that the GREEN-LOG project encompasses the necessary knowledge to certify the European relevance of its objectives and tasks, a panel of external visionary scientific and industrial experts has been established to perform independent evaluation of the key GREEN-LOG research activities, dissemination, and exploitation plans.

The External Advisory Board (EAB) has a multifaceted role in GREEN-LOG. The Board aims to contribute to the attainment of high-quality project outcomes and provide input concerning stakeholder requirements, societal and users’ priorities, regulations, and socio-economic impacts and exploitation, hence maximising impact and outcomes uptake. The EAB will also support the dissemination of project results through their networks.

The Board comprising 5 experts has been established in M03 of the project. Being an Innovation Action project, GREEN-LOG paid particular attention to the selection of the EAB members, ensuring representation from several sectors and different EU countries (including the those of the GREEN-LOG LLs). The list of the members is the following:

- Mr. Filip Goossens - Managing Director of On Time Logistics, a courier company in Antwerp with solutions for sustainable urban logistics, including cargo-bikes;
- Prof. Vasilis Zeimpekis, President of the Hellenic Logistics Association;
- Mr. Nikos Rodopoulos, President and Director of the Online Data AE and former President of the Hellenic Logistics Company;
- Prof. Rosário Macário, University of Lisbon, Portugal;
- Prof. Francesco Russo, Mediterranean University of Reggio Calabria, Italy.

The EAB members have been requested to sign a Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA) that specifies the relationship between them and the consortium and confidentiality restrictions.

The consortium prepared a plan for the involvement of the EAB members, including the list of the deliverables that are prioritised to be reviewed by the external experts and other activities (meetings, workshops, etc.) where the engagement of the specific EAB member would be highly beneficial.

⁴¹ <https://eclf.bike/index.html>

⁴² <https://eurocities.eu/>

Three EAB members, namely Mr. Phillip Goossens, Prof. Rosário Macário and Prof. Francesco Russo, following the invitation by the project consortium, joined the three of the GREEN-LOG co-creation Living Labs workshops (Flanders, Barcelona and Ispra respectively) in order to get acquainted with the project, the specific Living Labs and the use cases.

More information about the workshops is available in the section 6.3.

Further activities involving the EAB members will be implemented in the coming months following the abovementioned plan, which is being regularly evaluated and adjusted to the needs of the project at the specific time.

6.3 GREEN-LOG Co-creation Living Lab workshops

Local workshops, including those for the co-design endeavour in the definition of the Living Lab's activities, have been organised. At a later stage, similar workshops will be organised to disseminate pilot activities and results to external stakeholders. These will be carefully planned and organised after project partners have concluded actions to acquire a good understanding of the market and users' needs. They will take the form of both online and in-person events, according to the most cost-effective opportunities available. POLIS will facilitate Dissemination and Communication efforts, spreading the message among its media channels and newsletter addressed network of public local authorities and universities.

The goal of these workshops was to identify the key influencing factors of urban freight and service demand, considering transition impacts, emerging challenges, and innovations of last-mile solutions without forgetting any arising synergy effects with the current status quo.

The consortium will also investigate the possibility of organising local interactive workshops on the potential transferability and adaptability of the GREEN-LOG solutions developed within the project.

Ispra

The first workshop in this round was held on 29 September, in Ispra (Italy), bringing together stakeholders and final users to discuss and co-create innovative last-mile delivery solutions for the Ispra Living Lab in GREEN-LOG.

The event counted nine participants on site, including Living Lab partners and representatives from the Joint Research Centre (including canteen and site management, logistics providers, etc.), who will be the final users of the solutions to be developed. Eighteen participants joined the event online, including GREEN-LOG partners and follower city representatives from Arad, Romania.

The exchange focused on addressing the unique challenges and needs of the site, to co-create efficient, environmentally friendly, and socially beneficial services, while exploring synergies within the ecosystem. The event was an initial step towards defining the Living Lab solutions, in an iterative process between project-level partners and local stakeholders. The exchange produced relevant conclusions and insights into the work to be carried out.

Figure 23: GREEN-LOG Ispra Workshop

Barcelona

The workshop on “Co-Creating Next-Generation Last-Mile Solutions” took place on 16 November, in Barcelona, bringing together stakeholders, and final users to discuss and co-create innovative last-mile delivery solutions for the Barcelona Living Lab in GREEN-LOG.

The event counted 17 participants on site, including the Living Lab (LL) partners, and representatives from some of the sectors with whom the project will collaborate – namely, the Barcelona Municipality and the Metropolitan logistics research community. A further 20+ participants joined the event online, including the representatives from the municipalities of Sant Cugat and Terrassa, GREEN-LOG partners and follower city representatives from Arad, Romania.

Figure 24: GREEN-LOG Barcelona Workshop

Barcelona’s Living Lab is formed by a group of partners that harness the broad variety of competencies needed to establish multi-modal solutions (AIMSUN, ATM, EURECAT, Factual, FGC, Mosaic Factor and VANaPED). The workshop was the ideal setting for partners to validate their User Stories and to engage with a range of stakeholders. The exchange focused on addressing the unique opportunities and challenges of a corridor linking VANaPED’s cargo-bike hub in the centre of Barcelona with inland parts of the city served by FGC’s Vallès rail line, considering an extension further inland to cities such as Sabadell, Terrassa and Sant Cugat. The event was an initial step in validating the ways the Living Lab team is proposing to demonstrate multi-modal sustainable logistics services that integrate rail with cargo bikes, e-van and e-scooter options while simultaneously exploring how robots, modelling tools and APP-based incentives could support optimal configuration of the logistics chain(s).

Oxfordshire

The workshop on “Co-Creating Next-Generation Last-Mile Solutions” was held on 1 December, in Oxford (United Kingdom), bringing together stakeholders to discuss and co-create innovative last-mile delivery solutions for the Oxfordshire Living Lab in the GREEN-LOG project.

Twenty participants joined the event on site, among which representatives from Living Lab partners Oxfordshire County Council, FEED, Pedal & Post and University of Wolverhampton, as well as Oxford City Council, Oxford University, Oxford Brookes University, Oxford Covered Market, among others.

The exchange centred on addressing the challenges and needs of Oxford, to co-create efficient, environmentally friendly, and socially beneficial services, while exploring synergies within the ecosystem. The event was an initial step in the definition of the Living Lab solutions, in an iterative process between project-level partners and local stakeholders. Despite being an initial exchange, it yielded relevant conclusions and valuable insights that will inform the next stages of the project.

Figure 25: GREEN-LOG Oxfordshire Workshop

Specifically, Living Lab activities in Oxford will focus on the development of innovative models to scale up cargo-bike logistics services in the city. Three interdependent solutions will be tested including a moveable consolidation hub, an e-commerce platform for local traders, and a self-driven micro delivery hub to support cargo-bike logistics operations. These solutions are envisaged to increase the capacity, availability, and convenience of zero-emission and congestion reducing last-mile delivery in Oxford City.

Flanders

Stakeholders from Ghent, Mechelen and Leuven, convened for the GREEN-LOG Co-Creation Workshops held in Flanders, Belgium, on 6 and 9 February 2024. The workshops looked into crucial discussions surrounding the added value and value proposition of sustainable logistics solutions for urban environments in the Region.

The workshop started with an insightful exploration of the specific benefits and advantages expected from the implementation of the proposed solution in the Flanders Living Lab – the development of a Logistics as a Service (LaaS) platform in the above-mentioned cities.

The future LaaS platform is seen as a key solution for managing the complex landscape of urban logistics. LaaS not only offers a platform for stakeholder collaboration but also facilitates transparent communication, dynamic pricing, and nudging strategies. By aligning with local freight policy objectives and considering factors such as delivery speed, price, and quality, LaaS aims to improve accessibility, profitability, and efficiency while meeting diverse consumer needs.

Stakeholders identified key challenges prevalent in Living Labs, including ensuring accessibility, profitability, and efficiency amidst legislative requirements and logistical complexities. Addressing these challenges head-on, the workshop highlighted the significance of establishing clear regulatory frameworks, fostering collaboration among stakeholders, and meeting diverse consumer expectations.

Figure 26: GREEN-LOG Flanders Workshop

Athens

The GREEN-LOG project workshop held in Athens, organised by project partners ACS SMSA and the University of the Aegean, brought together stakeholders to discuss and strategise the implementation of sustainable and efficient parcel distribution solutions for the city.

The workshop commenced with a warm welcome from Athen's leading partner ACS SMSA, setting the tone for an engaging and collaborative session. University of the Aegean representatives, expressing gratitude for ACS SMSA hosting the event, initiated discussions with a thought-provoking icebreaker on online purchasing challenges, laying the groundwork for the workshop.

Attendees highlighted concerns related to online shopping experiences, including reliability issues, inconvenient delivery locations, absence of late-night deliveries, difficulties in contacting courier companies, and long queues at delivery points. These insights fuelled discussions on refining the GREEN-LOG project to address these pain points.

Figure 27: GREEN-LOG Athens Workshop

6.4 Capacity Building

Utilising the experience and results from the Living Labs, GREEN-LOG will deliver a Capacity Building Programme including training and open-source packages directed at seeing the GREEN-LOG Sustainable Solutions for the Last-mile building blocks broadly exploited in Europe and beyond, whilst also enabling knowledge sharing across the GREEN-LOG's network. POLIS leads this task, as it brings in its competencies in capacity building and knowledge transfer methodologies (online courses, training sessions, work shadowing, mentoring, peer-to-peer reviews, study visits), which have been implemented in various domains through EU-funded projects.

GREEN-LOG will establish a mechanism to facilitate knowledge sharing and enable the exchange between experts, by defining a methodology for the design and management of training offerings and developing dynamic courses in a flexible and modular format so that they are continuously updated.

Despite the project being in its early stages, the partners responsible for the task decided to kick off the conceptualisation process of the Capacity Building activities to ensure a smooth process.

The following are the main activities planned for the GREEN-LOG Capacity Building, with some initial angles to be explored:

1. Create a trusted community of knowledge exchange to encourage the interactive sharing of knowledge and best practices between participants, led by POLIS
 - The primary target to create this community will be the stakeholders in the Living Labs ecosystem. The further identification of these stakeholders will be done closely with the local partners.
2. Develop a training curriculum, training materials and tutorials to support actors who wish to use the augmented intelligence modelling services and enhance their skills toward planning and deploying modern logistics solutions, led by AIMSUM and POLIS, with the support of MOSAIC
 - There are two main target audiences defined:

- Internally, focusing on LL ecosystems: Logistics operators & City authorities
 - Externally, we will focus on the same typology of stakeholders, but external to the project⁴³
- Living Labs will develop use cases for both audiences, which can potentially be reflected in the development of the training curriculum.
3. Develop 3 online training modules and video tutorials, led by POLIS with support from AIMSUM, MOSAIC and academic partners
 - One of the topics to be addressed will be demonstration videos of the Augmented Intelligence Modelling Platform. These will focus on the theory behind it, as well as on providing a practical demonstration of the tool – potentially addressing the Living Lab use cases to be defined.
 4. Organise hands-on training workshops/labs on the solutions and use of GREEN-LOG for at least 50 stakeholders from industrial entities and authorities. This will provide the opportunity for hands-on experimentation, amplifying the opportunities for participants to learn, develop, and apply the new skills, led by POLIS.

GREEN-LOG will feed and include the material developed by GREEN-LOG on the E-course on CIVITAS Learning Centre⁴⁴, via the partners directly involved in the CIVITAS Initiative. The CIVITAS Learning Centre offers a suite of online e-courses that includes different topics that are available to anyone who wants to increase their knowledge of sustainable urban mobility.

GREEN-LOG will include the topics of City Logistics Living Labs and the Sustainable Solutions for the Last-mile within the CIVITAS e-courses, which are continuously being expanded. The consortium will explore other options for hosting the online courses as well.

In the first half of 2024, the discussions surrounding Capacity Building focused on:

- Identification of target audiences,
- Assessment of budgetary needs,
- Reflection on formats, duration and timing for training,
- Identification of potential topics for training, together with prioritisation by consortium partners.

This process resulted in a preliminary co-created list of 17 topics addressed by the project and its solutions. The list was shared with partners, who signalled those topics which are a priority for Capacity Building. These were – in order of importance:

- Lessons Learnt, Roadmap & Policy Recommendations for the alignment of SUMP/SULPs with the view of greening the last mile through cooperative approaches and optimising road transport;

⁴³ We can potentially benefit from cooperation activities within CIVITAS and ALICE-ETP (i.e. Urban Logistics Innovation Days), events co-organised with sister projects (i.e. DECARBOMILE to organise workshops in September 2025: assess the possibility of GREEN-LOG training back to back)

⁴⁴ <https://civitas.eu/learning-centre>

- Best practices, lessons learnt and impacts from analysis;
- Last-mile solutions Assessment, Transferability and Adaptability Framework
- Living Lab methodologies, focusing on elements of public-private cooperation;
- Specific material results from GREEN-LOG Demonstrations on multi-stakeholder collaborations for shared CCs and optimised cargo-bike; last-mile Logistics as a Service marketplace multimodal last-mile deliveries, next-generation last-mile delivery modes integrating delivery robots and AVs.

Most of the topics identified by partners as priorities for Capacity Building are general and relate to different activities to be carried out. Thus, in the cases in which that is possible, the next step will be the definition of timing for results readiness, considering priority topics chosen, to allow for a scheduling of potential activities together with the final decision on training formats. As for the more general topics, POLIS and WP leaders will discuss and identify – together with Living Lab partners – what subtopics and tools/solutions to focus on.

Some additional topics – not initially listed – were also brought up, namely:

- User/community engagement;
- Living Lab Methodology, also including “individual humans” as end-consumers;
- Dynamic pricing;
- Nudging strategies.

GREEN-LOG will organise training workshops to bring updated knowledge and improve the capabilities and skills of personnel working in the public sector (cities and local authorities). Concurrently, even if the Capacity Building activities will build upon GREEN-LOG results, we will assess the relevance of counting with inputs from other EU-funded projects and initiatives:

- Build upon the results of UlaaDS and SENATOR and focus more on the urban freight dimension (i.e., involving the lighthouse cities of UlaaDS and technical partners and the citizen engagement and co-creation component of SENATOR).
- Involve additional urban-freight-related projects, such as DISCO, DECARBOMILE, URBANE, UNCHAIN, and gather relevant knowledge also from the activities taking place in their pilots, to assess comparisons.

Further, GREEN-LOG will explore other potential synergies for capacity building, namely through resources and activities of the EIT Urban Mobility Training and the Living-in.EU initiative.

7 Standardisation Activities

GREEN-LOG foresees to observe the developments of CEN/TC 278 Intelligent transport systems. The consortium will seek collaboration with a number of its working groups to ensure that all services developed in the project comply with relevant standardisation processes, but also to contribute to the new processes when appropriate. Within this light, from the inception phase the consortium has investigated and preliminary identified the most applicable working groups where we can contribute depending on the project findings as these are reflected in section 2.2.4 of the Grant Agreement Part B.

Moreover, GREEN-LOG plan to adopt and, where necessary, extend specific standards in the ITS area, including among other, the DATEX-II²³ for real time traffic information and the GML Schema²⁴. The project also seeks to be involved in forming recommendations for bike infrastructure design and to provide directions to be included in national²⁵ and EU guides for cycling.

8 Planning and Monitoring

The WP5 leader (INTRA) is responsible for the close monitoring and evaluation of the implementation of all planned communication and dissemination activities. The evaluation of the communication and dissemination plan concerns both qualitative and quantitative indicators.

8.1 Roadmap of Activities

The following table (Table 4) presents the major Communication, Dissemination and Standardisation activities scheduled for the project course (this Roadmap will be updated and adjusted if needed during the project).

Table 5: Major Communication, Dissemination, Liaison, and Standardisation activities

Mechanisms/Activities	Description	Timeline	Responsibility/Involvement	STATUS
Visual identity				
GREEN-LOG logo and visual identity	The GREEN-LOG logo has been designed and will be used in all documents and publications of the project	M1	INTRA	Completed
GREEN-LOG presentation/deliverable/agenda/minutes templates	Templates to be used for the project deliverables/presentations	M1-2 (ppt template updated on M5)	INTRA	Completed
Web-based Communication				
Project website	Online presence of GREEN-LOG	M4 (landing page was in place since M2)	POLIS (INTRA support)	Completed
Social Media package <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LinkedIn company page • Twitter • YouTube channel 	Social Media accounts for disseminating project news, developments and results	M1	POLIS (INTRA support)	Completed
e-Newsletter	Diffusing project news, achievements, and events, in the form of an e-Newsletter	Templates ready on M3, updated on M6, issues publication : M6-M42	INTRA	Ongoing

Third-party non-scientific publications / media (EU channels, industry magazines, third-party portals, e-newsletters, blogs, (e-)newspapers, etc.)	Articles introducing GREEN-LOG, its achievements, and results to be published on 3rd party portals and the relevant media	M2-M42	ALL	Ongoing
Audio visual and multimedia	Multimedia content (video, images, illustrations) presenting GREEN-LOG context and solutions to support awareness creation and	M7-M42	INTRA, ALL	Ongoing
Events				
Participation in events (i.e., conferences, workshops)	Participation in events (i.e., conferences, workshops, local events) to raise awareness about GREEN-LOG and disseminate the project's concepts and results	M1-M42	ALL	Ongoing
Events organisation (i.e., workshops, final event, etc.)	Organisation of workshops, trainings, webinars, conference, etc.	M03-M42	ALL	Ongoing
Promotional material				
Online and printed Dissemination material (i.e., leaflets)	Prepare, upload on the website and print the material to create awareness of the project	M6, updated content: after M18	INTRA, agreed with all	1 st version leaflet available and updated with new partners
Light-weight exhibition material				
Roll-up	Prepare and make available to the partners and, when appropriate, print the material to be used during the events and other activities	M6	INTRA, agreed with all	Completed and updated with new partners' logos
Press-based Communication				
Press releases	Press Releases (during important moments)	M2-M42	INTRA	Ongoing
Scientific publications				
Scientific papers and publications	Several publications are expected in conferences and in journals	M2 – M42	ALL	Ongoing
Collaboration with other projects and initiatives				

Synergies with other projects	Activities launched (internal verifications and list update, planning activities) and ongoing	M1-M42	INTRA, ALL (who is linked with any project)	Ongoing
EU, national and international initiatives	Activities launched (internal verifications and list update, planning activities) and ongoing	M1-M42	INTRA, ALL (who is linked with any initiative)	Ongoing
Standardisation activities				
Standardisation activities	Relevant standardisation groups to be identified/verified, and activities planned and launched	Approx. M18-M42	Relevant partners	Mostly planned for the second half of the project,

8.2 Monitoring Tool

With the aim to collect and monitor information related to the Communication, Dissemination and Liaison activities implemented by the partners, a common online plan and reporting Excel document (Tracker) consisting of nine sheets has been placed on the project's SharePoint, and the reminder to keep it updated is regularly shared with all the partners. The Tracker consists of the following sheets:

- 01 - Events: collecting the events that the partners will participate/(co-)organise throughout the project together with the respective reports.
- 02 - Scientific publications: collects the papers submitted by the partners to conferences and scientific journals.
- 03 - Media articles: collects the list of the articles or other pieces of information about GREEN-LOG in the media or other third-party websites/blogs/intranets.
- 04 - Partners' websites, news: mentions of the GREEN-LOG project on partners' websites.
- 05 - Other Dissemination and Communication Activities: collects information on the complementary individual activities of the partners within the scope and framework of the Communication/Dissemination plan of the project.
- 06 - Synergies with projects: collects the liaising activities of the project and project partners with other projects.
- 07 - Associations, Initiatives: collects the liaising activities of the project and project partners with various initiatives.
- 08 - Standards (to be) adopted
- 09 - Standardisation activities
- 10 - Blog posts calendar: calendar for the partners to provide content for the project's blog.

- 11 - Social media rotation plan: the rotation plan for the partners to provide the social media posts to be published through the project's social media channels.

All partners recognise that dissemination and communication activities are an essential and pervasive activity throughout the project's life and integrate within all its work packages. The overview of information gathered through the tool can be found in the Appendix.

8.3 Key Performance Indicators

The effectiveness of the dissemination, as well as of the communication, activities will be assessed during the life of the project and the results of these assessments will be presented in each reporting period.

Table 6: Communication and Dissemination Activities Impact

Expected Impact	Related KPI	M18	Final Target
Increased collaboration with other initiatives; Synergies establishment for joint research, information exchange and dissemination. Increased awareness.	# of workshops organised, incl. demos	7	10
	# of multi-stakeholders events	7	12
Ideas' gathering and knowledge exchange with relevant communities and initiatives; Information about latest technologies/advantages; Liaisons with other initiatives.	# of attended events	16	40
	# of events with project's presentation	12	20
Validation of the project's concept, findings and advantages; Promotion of results to scientific communities; Ideas' gathering and knowledge exchange with relevant communities and initiatives.	# of conference papers	3 accepted + 2 submitted	30
	# of journal papers	1	15
	# of articles in industry magazines	Planned for 2nd reporting period	20
Communication of project news, events & results; Validation of project's concept, finding and advantages; Ideas' gathering and knowledge exchange; Increased awareness.	# of industry contact points	Approx. 80	200
	# of industry communities informed about the project	A concrete number is difficult to be provided. People & communities are reached during the events and through partners' collaboration activities	15
Knowledge exchange; Mutual validation of results; Joint dissemination activities; Attraction of	# of projects with synergies	13	15

potential partners for research collaborations.	# of joint activities	4 (incl. joint stands, joint paper and joint promotional material)	5
Communication of project news, events & results; Validation of project's concept, finding and advantages; Ideas' gathering and knowledge exchange; Increased awareness.	# of internal partners' events	>7	30
	# of links to the project's website	>14	50
	# of training webinars	n.a. yet	5
Communication of project results; Validation of project's concept, findings and advantages; Increased awareness.	# of working groups	n.a.	3
	# of project presentations in standardisation meetings	1 planned	5
	# of actors reached	A concrete number is difficult to be provided. People are reached during the events and through partners' collaboration activities	>300
Main online information point; Communication of project news, events & results; Liaisons with other initiatives, and projects through links; Increased awareness.	# of unique visitors	3400	1000
	Average duration of visits	1 minute, 5 seconds	5 minutes
	Of page views	11000	3000
Increasing visibility to stakeholders active in social media; Attainment of interest of stakeholders; Viral marketing by "word of mouth" through the followers; Direct Communication mechanism with followers.	# of cumulative followers	720	300
	# of cumulative posts	240	30
	# of interactions	59	1000
Communication of the main project's concepts and advantages in an easily understandable manner.	# of posts	13 (blog posts)	20
	# of interactions	n.a.	1000
Communication of project news, events & results; Increased awareness.	# of press releases	2 (EN) + 2 (RO)	7
Unique branding and visual identity of the project; Provision of instant information about the project; Creating a unified experience for the audiences targeted; Communication of results and information provision during events.	# of project factsheets/brochures and banners	3	5
	# of e-newsletters	3	8
	# of videos	1	5
	# of blog posts in EU Mechanisms	2	15
Patent filed at the European Patent Office, protecting strategic EU IP	# Patents	0	1
Capacity Building	# of students enrolled on e-courses	n.a.	200

9 Conclusion

This deliverable builds upon the strategy defined in the Communication, Dissemination and Liaison plan, presenting the initial outcomes of these activities during the first 18 months of the project, namely from January 2023 to June 2024.

Following the strategies and approaches identified in the plan, the consortium participated in various relevant activities, including among other participation to European and international conferences and events, organisation of workshops, publishing of scientific papers, collaboration with relevant initiatives and other projects in the field, further definition of Capacity building as well as the utilisation of diverse channels for disseminating project results. These efforts aim to reach the project's targeted stakeholders, but also a broader audience, promote knowledge sharing, and facilitate the demonstration of project outcomes. The material produced, including leaflets, roll-up, newsletters, videos, the regularly updated website and social media channels, play a crucial role in presenting the project and its achievements.

In order to measure the progress and impacts of different activities and means, a monitoring and evaluation framework has been defined and a series of indicators (KPIs) have been set and measured.

GREEN-LOG has been successful in progressing in most of the established targets, as evidenced in this document. The analysis presented will allow the project's communication and dissemination team to course correct, implementing a close follow-up to ensure that the objectives defined are achieved.

This document will be further updated in two additional moments, with D5.4: Dissemination/Communication Strategy & Kit / Activities Report 3rd Version and D5.5: Dissemination/Communication Strategy & Kit / Activities Report Final Version.

Appendix A

List of events in which GREEN-LOG participated.

Event & Date	Location	Partner	Type of participation	Target Audience
Virtual Breakfast on urban freight International Women's Day – 8/03/2023	Online	INTRA	Round table discussion	Research communities, EU Institutions, International organisations, Experts in the area
1st REBEL lunch&learn Seminar: Beyond the Living Lab - past, present, futures, 29/03/2023	Halmstad & Online	Halm	Moderation	Research communities, EU projects, local authorities
2nd REBEL L&L Seminar: Co-designing future mobility - how to stage cross-sectoral and inter-generational design practices, 10/05/2023	Halmstad & Online	Halm	Moderation (V.Fors), Guest researcher (J.Lund)	Research communities, EU projects, local authorities
9th International Physical Internet Conference - IPIC2023, 13-15/06/2023	Athens, Greece	INTRA, UoA	Participated in a meeting with sister projects	Research communities, Industry/business partners, Innovators, International organisations, Civil society
World Conference on Transport Research, 17-21/07/2023	Montreal, Canada	UoA	Presentation	Experts in all areas of transport research, policy makers
Artificial Intelligence made easy for Railway and Mobility Value Chain, 7-8/06/2023	Florence, Italy	EURECAT	Roundtable discussion	EU institutions, Railway stakeholders, academic community, AI and Big data based companies
Urban Logistics Innovation Day 2023, 26/09/2023	Brussels, Belgium	POLIS	Displayed roll-up and leaflets	Industry/business partners, EU Institutions, Regional Authorities, Local authorities

Urban Mobility Days Conference, 4-6/10/2023	Sevilla, Spain	INTRA, EURECAT, UAEGEAN, POLIS, MobyX, FI, UoW	Booth, pitch session, leaflets, Roll-up	policymakers, local authorities, academics, NGOs, urban transport practitioners and more
VREF International Urban Freight Conference, 18/10/2023	Gothenburg, Sweden	UoA	Poster Presentation	Research and practitioners
ULaaDS final event, 15-16/11/2023	Barcelona, Spain	EURECAT	Presentation	Local authorities, research communities, innovators, industry partners, international organisations,
2023 Annual POLIS conference, 29-30/12/2023	Leuven, Belgium	LEU presented on freight, Claudia (POLIS), Joris B. (UoA (not presenting))	Presentation	Local authorities, research communities, innovators, industry partners, international organisations
Green Technologies, Energy and Digitalisation for a Sustainable Future, 12/02/2024	Ljubljana, Slovenia	INTRA	Participation and networking	
Data Week 2024 (under the umbrella of the Data Spaces Symposium 2024), 13/03/2024	Darmstadt, Germany	INTRA	Participation and networking	industry players, associations, researchers, innovators, and policymakers

TRA2024, 15-18/04/2024	Dublin, Ireland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - INTRA, FI, POLIS - UoA - paper - UAEGEAN & HALM - paper - e-Novia sent a droid and a cargo-bike to the EC JRC stand 	Joint paper with sister projects, GREEN-LOG presented at the joint session of some UF projects, joint stand at the ALICE Innovation Village, Yape droid and Measy cargo-bike at the EC JRC stand and the outdoor exhibition	..Researchers, Policy-makers, and industry representatives
2nd CIVINET Forum, 28-30/05/2024	Athens, Greece	INTRA	Presentation, networking	politicians, mobility practitioners, researchers, students, industry representatives, start-uppers, civil society members, creative artists, and citizens
Urban Logistics Innovation Day, 4/06/2024	Brussels, Belgium	POLIS (as organisers), UoA - Joris (as a presenter)	Presentation	Industry/business partners, EU Institutions, Regional Authorities, Local authorities

Scientific Publications or Conference Proceedings

Type	Title	Authors	Title of Journal/Proceedings	Number, date or frequency	Status
Article in Journal	Exploring Logistics-as-a-Service to integrate the consumer into urban freight	Joris Beckers, Ivan Cardenas, Michela Le Pira, Jia Zhang	Research in Transportation Economics	Volume 101, November 2023, 101354	Published
Publication in Conference proceedings/Wor	Establishing and evaluating Living Labs for city logistics: Challenges and opportunities	Karakikes Ioannis, Fors Vaike, Lund Jesper, Polydoropoulou Amalia, Mavrogenidou Panagiota	TBA (TRA 2024 proceedings)		Accepted

kshop					
Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	Integrating a white-label scheme service for a shared micro consolidation centre in Athens, Greece	Karakikes Ioannis, Polydoropoulou Amalia, Athena Tsirimpa	TBA (CSUM 2024 proceedings)		Accepted
Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	Decarbonising last mile logistics	Manon Levrey, Amalia Ntemou, Akrivi Kiousi, Ioanna Fergadiotou, Maria Kampa, Dimitrios Rizopoulos, Babis Magoutas, Athena Tsirimpa, Panos Georgakis	TBA (TRA 2024 proceedings)		Accepted
Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	How to stage and assess processes of co-creation in Living Labs: A Design Ethnographic approach	Gregor Cerinsek, Melania Mihalcea, Vaike Fors	OLL24		Submitted
Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	Co-Creative Filmmaking for Integration of User Perspectives in Living Lab Environments	Melania Mihalcea, Gregor Cerinsek, Vaike Fors	OLL24		Submitted
Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	Next generation last mile delivery integrating delivery robots and cargo bikes	Ioannis Karakikes, Eleonora Di Fabio, Matteo Mazzucchelli, Federico Moro, Amalia Polydoropoulou	TRB (TRB 2025)		Planned